

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Administrative Office: GHS Road, Mangalore-575 001, Phone 0824-2425966

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Akshatha bearing USN No. 8SU22ED001 has completed minor project on “Learning difficulties in reading lessons” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Akshatha B bearing USN No. 8SU22ED002 has completed minor project on “Attitude of students towards learning” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Aleena Roy Joseph bearing USN No. 8SU22ED003 has completed minor project on “Speaking skills in first language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Anagha M bearing USN No. 8SU22ED004 has completed minor project on “Errors in writing second language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Ananya Rao bearing USN No. 8SU22ED005 has completed minor project on “Lack of communication skills” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Jayashree'.

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This is to certify that Ms. Anima Lakra bearing USN No. 8SU22ED006 has completed minor project on “Difficulties in identifying places in maps” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Apeksha Rai bearing USN No. 8SU22ED007 has completed minor project on “Lack of knowledge about writing skills” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Asha bearing USN No. 8SU22ED008 has completed minor project on “Lack of knowledge about writing skills in Hindi” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Asmina bearing USN No. 8SU22ED009 has completed minor project on “Low achievement in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Athulya M K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED010 has completed minor project on “Lack of interest towards learning English” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Ayshath Safwana bearing USN No. 8SU22ED011 has completed minor project on “Phobia in solving mathematical problems” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Chaithra bearing USN No. 8SU22ED012 has completed minor project on “Low achievement in mathematics” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Deepika C.T bearing USN No. 8SU22ED013 has completed minor project on “Lack of handling equipment’s in science lab” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Divyashree A bearing USN No. 8SU22ED014 has completed minor project on “General intelligence of students” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Fathimath Bushra bearing USN No. 8SU22ED015 has completed minor project on “Lack of recalling biological terms” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Fathimath Faaiza bearing USN No. 8SU22ED016 has completed minor project on “Creativity in teaching Biology” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Mr. Harikrishnan P K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED017 has completed minor project on “Different Techniques of learning” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Harshitha K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED018 has completed minor project on “Different Techniques of learning Biology” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Harshitha Shetty M bearing USN No. 8SU22ED019 has completed minor project on “Social intelligence of students” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Harshitha V bearing USN No. 8SU22ED020 has completed minor project on “Errors in writing Kannada language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Hazra Safeeqa bearing USN No. 8SU22ED021 has completed minor project on “Reading difficulties in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Jeena R bearing USN No. 8SU22ED022 has completed minor project on “Different Techniques of teaching Mathematics” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Kavya Krishnan M bearing USN No. 8SU22ED023 has completed minor project on “Lack of handling equipment’s in science lab” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Keerthi Vijayan bearing USN No. 8SU22ED024 has completed minor project on “General class room problems” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Kyntiewbha Shabong bearing USN No. 8SU22ED025
has completed minor project on “Difficulties in reading biological terms” in the I
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This is to certify that Ms. Madhuri Minz bearing USN No. 8SU22ED026 has completed minor project on “Lack of interest towards learning English” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Melna Benny bearing USN No. 8SU22ED027 has completed minor project on “Lack of understating basic concepts of commerce” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Mr. Midhun Jophy bearing USN No. 8SU22ED028 has completed minor project on “Emotional Quotient of students” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Mr. Najeeb PH bearing USN No. 8SU22ED029 has completed minor project on “Study on adjustment problems within the peer groups” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Nireeksha S Nayak bearing USN No. 8SU22ED030 has completed minor project on “Behavioural problems of students” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Priya U G bearing USN No. 8SU22ED032 has completed minor project on “Lack of importance of education” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Rekha Regisamam bearing USN No. 8SU22ED033 has completed minor project on “Reading difficulties in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Rithika bearing USN No. 8SU22ED034 has completed minor project on “Lack of sentence formation while writing essay in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Safiya Shera Akrami bearing USN No. 8SU22ED035 has completed minor project on “Attitude of students towards learning Biology” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Shetty Preksha Gunapal bearing USN No. 8SU22ED036
has completed minor project on “Social intelligence of students” in the I year of
B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Shilpa Shetty bearing USN No. 8SU22ED037 has completed minor project on “Lack of interest towards learning English” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Shwetha bearing USN No. 8SU22ED038 has completed minor project on “Lack of using geometrical instruments” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Sneha V bearing USN No. 8SU22ED039 has completed minor project on “Lack of memorizing tables in mathematics” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Sowmyashree K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED040 has completed minor project on “Lack of knowledge of vocabulary in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Sruthi C bearing USN No. 8SU22ED041 has completed minor project on “Attitude of students towards learning Mathematics” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Suma S K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED042 has completed minor project on “Errors in writing Kannada language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Thanveera A C bearing USN No. 8SU22ED043 has completed minor project on “Low achievement in Biology” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Uchil Chaitra Nagesh bearing USN No. 8SU22ED044 has completed minor project on “Low achievement in Social Science” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Vidhupriya K K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED045 has completed minor project on “Lack of using geometrical instruments” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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This is to certify that Ms. Vidya K bearing USN No. 8SU22ED046 has completed minor project on “Communication skills in first language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Jayashree'.

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This is to certify that Ms. Vidya M Rao bearing USN No. 8SU22ED047 has completed minor project on “Lack of sentence formation while writing essay in language” in the I year of B.Ed. programme for the academic year 2022-23.

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